

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

WP1 SETTING LEGAL AND SOCIAL CONDITIONS

D1.5 CIRCULAR APPROACH MODEL

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¹ PU= Public, SEN=Sensitive

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

AHV	Anchor Handling Vessel
CTV	Crew Transport Vessel
EoL	End-of-Life
EU	European Union
FCR	Feed Conversion Rate
FSV	Fast Supply Vessels
FU	Functional Unit
HLV	Heavy Lift Vessel
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MUP	Multi-use Project
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
SPMT	Self-Propelled Modular Transporter
TRL	Technological Readiness Level

Executive summary

This document outlines a circularity model for a multi-use project (MUP) combining offshore wind energy and aquaculture devices. This model serves as a tool for comparing various scenarios, ranging from baseline to less carbon-intensive alternatives. The results are presented in terms of carbon emissions per kWh of electricity and per kg of fish produced to allow for comparison with previous studies.

A comprehensive data collection was conducted from both project-specific information and pertinent literature, reports, and industry sources. The data gathered from the 1:6 scale prototype was extrapolated to evaluate the impact at full scale. Based on the baseline scenario, circular strategies such as recycling, reusing, lifetime extension, and use of alternative materials were considered to assess their potential to minimize the environmental impact. The main goal of this analysis is to identify the main contributors to carbon emissions in the system and identify opportunities for improvement.

It is important to note that the results presented in this document are based on a range of assumptions, which reflect the current Technological Readiness Level (TRL) of the project. Thus, although they provide valuable information, there is an associated degree of uncertainty. A more comprehensive examination of the carbon footprint will be carried out in “D4.4 -Environmental Impact Assessment” as part of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) study, offering further information on the project's carbon footprint.

1. Introduction

Offshore wind farms offer a range of advantages to aquaculture operations, fostering a symbiotic relationship between renewable energy generation and sustainable food production. The co-location of wind farms and aquaculture infrastructure optimises use of maritime space, as well as sharing mooring systems, thus significantly minimizing environmental impact. Multi-use projects increase resource efficiency, and reduce the waste stream, while collaborative maintenance efforts simplify operations, ultimately contributing to a more resilient marine ecosystem.

Traditional production models work within a linear approach, characterized by the sequential flow of new resources and materials into production systems, thus it is crucial to integrate circularity strategies. By implementing such strategies, the demand for critical materials will be reduced while enhancing economic efficiency and demonstrating social responsibility, which is imperative to achieve critical environmental targets such as those set by the European Union (EU) to reduce carbon emissions.

The results presented in this document derive from a model developed to integrate the principles of the circular economy, in which the recycling and reuse of resources are considered, thus reducing the need for new material inputs, and minimizing the production of waste. For this assessment, additional strategies were also considered, such as the alternative use of material inputs and the extension of lifetimes. At its core, this model seeks to optimize the synergy between aquaculture and offshore wind energy production. By incorporating circular economy principles into the value chain, this model not only enhances resource efficiency but also reduces the overall environmental impact of device implementation. Additionally, significant reductions in environmental impacts are observed in these analyses, highlighting the efficacy of this approach in promoting sustainability.

Through a high-level assessment, the total carbon footprint from the present project is evaluated, accounting for all stages of production from cradle to grave.

2. Methodology

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) serves as a method to identify and evaluate potential impacts associated with a specific product. The systematic procedures and guidelines are outlined by standards ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 [1] [2], and typically consist of four main stages:

- 1- Definition of the objective, scope, and functional unit.
- 2- Compiling an exhaustive inventory of all inputs and outputs.
- 3- Impact assessment according to predetermined impact categories.
- 4- Interpretation of the results, identifying significant environmental aspects.

Through this quantification, it is possible to identify the main critical points and propose strategies for minimising the impact. This study aims to develop a circular model based on the LCA approach to assess the potential carbon footprint of the AquaWind full-scale project composed of a single device with the net capacity to produce 50GWh of electricity and 400 tons of fish annually over 25 years.

As a MUP with two different outputs, the allocation approach is applied, with the Functional Units (FU) defined according to the output of each subsystem, i.e. 1 kWh of electricity delivered to the grid for the wind energy subsystem, and 1 kg of fish produced by the aquaculture subsystem. Applying an allocation approach in a hybrid project involves determining how to allocate environmental burdens and benefits between the different components of the project. This approach ensures that emissions are allocated appropriately based on the contribution of each output to the overall system.

The model was built in Excel and used as a reference for the main information on design, configuration, operating requirements and energy and fish production shared by the partners and the project's documents. Secondary data were based on the literature, technical expertise, discussion between the project's partners, and premises assumed to enable the assessment. The system boundary encompasses all life cycle stages from cradle to grave comprising the production of components, their assembly, transportation and installation, operation and maintenance (O&M), and finally decommissioning and end-of-life (EoL) strategies (Figure 1). The assessment focused on principal elements such as turbines, platform structure, mooring system, net cage, feeding system, and associated main elements, considering embodied carbon from materials, energy and fuel used in each process. The electrical cables, substation, and all parts of the onshore electricity grid are outside the scope of this analysis. Additionally, the analysis does not comprise the stages of fish processing and packaging.

Figure 1 – System Boundaries

The simplified flowchart of the life cycle considered in this analysis is indicated in Figure 2. This exercise presents a simplified illustration of the LCA methodology employed in a baseline scenario, to estimate the carbon footprint, and propose and demonstrate the advantages of implementing circularity strategies. Each circular approach and its assumptions will be further described in section 5.

Figure 2 – Flowchart of the lifecycle of the AquaWind Project

At this stage, the developed model only considers embodied carbon and no further impacts. A more detailed LCA is planned for deliverable D4.4 in order to refine the results as the project evolves. The findings from this analysis aim to inform decision-making within the AquaWind project and future research. However, the recommendations proposed in this document are exclusively related to carbon emissions and should be considered in conjunction with economic, technical, industrial, and other environmental analyses.

The CO₂ emissions rely on several factors, such as the weights of components, industrial processes, and manufacturing, deployment, and maintenance location. Given the current TRL of the project, some assumptions were considered in this study, which may lead to a certain level of uncertainty. As a result, the embodied carbon was estimated based on key premises adopted. Refinements of the project's design and variation of location may lead to different results.

3. Data collection

Foreground or primary data were collected mainly from the project team, material experts and engineers. All background or secondary data were ultimately derived from the Ecoinvent database (v.3.5) [3] and data sourced in the literature and reports. Some premises were assumed as certain criteria have still not been defined at this stage of the project. The key project parameters assumed to undertake the calculations are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 – Key parameters summary

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
<i>Project scale</i>	<i>1:1</i>
<i>Project configuration</i>	<i>W2Power + Aquaculture net cage</i>
<i>Location of deployment</i>	<i>Canary Islands</i>
<i>Number of devices</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Turbine installed capacity</i>	<i>2 x 5MW</i>
<i>Annual energy production</i>	<i>50 GWh</i>
<i>Annual fish production</i>	<i>400 tons</i>
<i>Operational lifetime</i>	<i>25 years</i>
<i>Distance from port</i>	<i>45 km</i>

3.1. Materials and Manufacturing

The initial phase delimited by the system starts with the processing of raw materials, followed by the manufacturing phase, in which the materials are moulded and shaped to produce the sub-components of the device.

As the information reported in D2.1, D2.2, D3.1 and D3.2 [4], [5], [6], [7] on the main specification concerns the 1:6 prototype, a scale up of the dimensions to collect full-scale requirements was attempted.

For a floating wind project with a capacity of 10MW (2 x 5MW turbines), the characteristics of 5MW turbine from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [8] were assumed, as well as the scale sizing of the floater, cage, and other components. It should be noted that no stability, hydrodynamic, structural, sea-keeping, or other aspects that could impact the system's technical performance were carried out for the dimensioning in question, and further refinement is recommended at a later stage.

The W2Power wind platform is a floating structure made primarily of steel and composed of three main columns and an auxiliary column, connected to each other by a bracing system that forms a triangle. Each column has a lifting plate that increases stability and provides buoyancy to the platform. The towers are located on the upper deck of each of the two main columns. The dimensioning of the full-scale platform [9] is considered as reference. It is assumed that steel passes through the processes of machining and welding before being painted to avoid biofouling and corrosion. The energy consumption for the heavy machining and painting processes was based on [10]. Calculations for the welding process were undergone assuming the need for 4,35 kg of welded steel per meter [11]. Steel is also the main material in the composition of turbine towers, nacelles, and rotors. The blades are composed of composite material, such as fibre glass and epoxy resin, in a proportion of 75% and 25% respectively.

The mooring system consists of 3 lines composed of alloy steel chains and nylon ropes, while the prefabricated anchors are made of cast iron. For a full-scale project and proposed location, the expected station-keeping loads and type of soil have not been analysed specifically. In this way, for this study, 3 anchors of 20 tons each were considered [12]. In this project, the mooring system is the element shared by the hybrid system. Identifying the total mass of the components and allocating it to each subsystem, it is estimated that 86% and 14% of the mooring system will be allocated to wind and aquaculture, respectively. This distribution is crucial to allocating the carbon footprint to each system. The design of AquaWind's prototype is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Prototype of the AquaWind Project

Regarding the aquaculture cage, a cylindrical mesh cage measuring 36 meters in diameter and 20 meters in depth is constructed using a wire blend of copper, tin, aluminium, and zinc. The materials were selected to optimise the lifetime of its structural elements, prevent corrosion and structural replacement, and avoid the use of anti-fouling products, bringing environmental and economic benefits. Flotation tubes made of polyethylene and filled with porexpan to ensure floatation are placed around the cage diameter.

For the purpose of fish cultivation, the initial fish mass to be introduced in the cage is set at 0.250 kg/fish, with the objective of achieving an annual biomass yield of 400 tons, each fish weighing around 2 kg at harvest. Accounting for an average Feed Conversion Rate (FCR) of 2 and ensuring a minimum feed reserve autonomy of 5 days, the metallic silo must hold a minimum of 9,6 tonnes of feed, requiring 10 silos of 190 kg each. It is considered that the active ballast will maintain the stability of the system according to the draining of the silos in the feed process.

To reach the targeted annual fish production, a total of 700 tonnes of feed is required throughout the year. The feed consists primarily of extruded pellets composed mainly of fish meal, soybeans, wheat grains, recycled fish, and fish oil [13]. According to [14], the daily energy demands associated with feeding, lighting, and maintenance correspond to approximately 0.022 kWh/day per ton of fish produced. This requires approximately 17 m² of photovoltaic solar panel coverage, distributed within 7 panels,

considering a 30% margin to ensure regular feed supply. Additionally, a set of batteries is considered to collect the surplus energy generated by the PV panels and with the capacity to guarantee 48 hours of autonomy.

The PV panels are composed mainly of silicon, glass, aluminium, ethylene vinyl acetate, and polyethene, in a proportion of 75%, 10%, 10%, 2.5% and 2.5%, respectively. Given the expected residual contribution of some electronic and electrical systems, to simplify this stage, it was considered an additional 10% of the total weight of the power system for other components. An estimate of the mass and material breakdown associated with the mentioned components is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** and **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4 - Subsystems – approximate mass breakdown

Figure 5 - Subsystems – approximate material breakdown

Considering the wind turbine system, the platform is the major contributor to the total demand for material (63%), followed by turbines (32%), which is a trend in this type of project. In this way, steel represents 95% of the total material of the whole system, summing up also other minor components of the wind and aquaculture system.

3.2. Assembly and Installation

For the full-scale project, the supply chain was not specified, so it was necessary to assume the manufacturing locations of the main materials and components. Considering the distance and the components' weight, transport to the assembly port was calculated in terms of payload. The payload, measured in tons per kilometers (tkm), denotes the transport of one tonne of goods by a specific mode of transport over one kilometre. The distance to the port was approximated by GoogleMaps for each trip assuming road and vessel freight transport.

During the assembly phase, each material and sub-component will be transported by road and sea to the assembly yard in the Canary Islands from their respective assumed manufacturing sites: steel and net cage (Germany), towers and nacelle (Spain), chain and anchors (UK), nylon ropes (Belgium), blades and rotor (Denmark), PV panels and other elements of the power system (China), while supports, silo and other structural subcomponents will be constructed in the Canary Islands.

Considering the floating structure, most of the assembly work can be done on land, allowing for less complex and more time-efficient processes. After final assembly, specialized vessels are required to perform the load-out and float-off of the platform, install the turbine, anchors, mooring lines and cage, tow the elements to the site deployment, transport specialized personnel and conduct final inspections. It is assumed that the platform and cage will be assembled at the nearest facility to the site and then towed to the installation location.

The equipment and vessels generally considered for installation and O&M are Cranes, Self-Propelled Modular Transporter (SPMT), Crew Transport Vessel (CTV), Fast Supply Vessels (FSV), Heavy Lift Vessel (HLV), Tugboat, Anchor Handling Vessel (AHV), and Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV). The estimated fuel consumption is based on a literature review performed by [12] and is indicated in Table 2.

Table 2 – Summary of vessels' speed and consumption

<i>Vessel</i>	<i>Speed</i>	<i>Fuel consumption</i>
<i>Crane</i>	-	200 kW/h
<i>SPMT</i>	-	47 l/h
<i>HLV</i>	11 km/h (transiting)	2266 l/h (transiting) 113 l/h (operating)
<i>Tug</i>	22 km/h (transiting) 6 km/h (towing)	448 l/h (transiting) 596 l/h (towing)
<i>AHV</i>	19 km/h (transiting) 6 (towing)	1046 l/h (transiting; operating) 1942 l/h (towing)
<i>ROV</i>	1.2 km/h (operating)	50 l/h

<i>CTV</i>	<i>44.5 km/h (transiting)</i>	<i>381 l/h (transiting)</i> <i>229 l/h (operating)</i>
<i>FSV</i>	<i>18.5 (transiting)</i>	<i>196 l/h (transiting)</i> <i>392 l/h (operating)</i>

Floating wind structures installation may range from approximately 60h to 120h, depending on the turbine capacity, complexity of the system and location of deployment. The assumed installation strategy was based on information provided by D2.2 and WavEC's expertise from previous studies. The key inputs considered include task duration, vessel types, and fuel consumption, without accounting for weather constraints and mobilization time. The summary of the vessels considered for this stage is detailed in Table 3.

Table 3 – Summary of installation tasks

Activity	Time estimated	Vessels
<i>Installation of 2 x 5MW hub and turbine</i>	<i>40 h</i>	<i>Crane + HLV</i>
<i>Load out, float off, towing and installation of platform</i>	<i>32 h</i>	<i>SPMT + HLV + Tug + AHV</i>
<i>Lift and installation of anchors; Installation of mooring lines; Inspection of mooring system</i>	<i>16 h</i>	<i>Crane + AHV + Tug + ROV</i>
<i>Load, towing and installation of cage</i>	<i>16 h</i>	<i>SPMT + Tug + AHV</i>
<i>Installation of silos, PV panels and other elements</i>	<i>24 h</i>	<i>FSV</i>

By scaling Ecoinvent data for a freight ship to match the total fuel consumption of each type of vessel, as suggested by [15], it is possible to estimate the correspondent payload of each operation, where 1 tkm corresponds to 0,0028 litres of fuel.

3.3. Operation and Maintenance

As the project still has no registered operation and maintenance data, the O&M analysis incorporates failure rates of main components for both the wind and aquaculture systems to estimate embodied carbon, primarily associated with vessel activities during the 25-year lifetime. It also considered the annual preventive campaigns and task duration. A tow-to-port strategy was contemplated for large repairs, aiming to avoid the use of large offshore vessels, and minimising risks, stoppages, expenditures, and emissions. The analysis employs a WavEC's in-house model for O&M of offshore turbines, complemented by other sources for aquaculture system maintenance [16].

In this simplified assessment, the potential loss of energy production due to stoppages caused by failures and maintenance activities was not taken into account. The model also considered the reliability of spare parts, which means that major repairs require that the generator and mooring line must be replaced 4 and 24 times each [12]. Regarding the power system used for the aquaculture device, it is assumed that the batteries and other electrical and electronic elements should be replaced every 4 years. Despite its occurrence during the maintenance phase, the burdens related to new components are allocated in the manufacturing and installation stages.

For the fish production system, a critical operational aspect involves transporting fish to the deployment site to be introduced in the cage for the growth phase and returning them to shore after annual harvesting. It was considered that the starting point from which the fish leave to be grown and the food production plant are both 50 km away from the port, requiring transport by truck and vessel. In this way, an annual transport by truck + vessel of initial biomass of fish of 50 tons (250g each) to the site and the reverse journey with grown fish (2kg each) totalling 400 tons at the end of 1 year is considered.

Additionally, it's vital to consider the frequency of trips to ensure a regular feed supply during this stage. The feeding operation involves a silo with a capacity for 5 days of feed autonomy, leading to an average of 73 trips per year to refill the storage. It was considered that the energy required for the feeding processes, as well as monitoring and lighting, is solar energy-based, implying no carbon emissions in the operation phase. Similarly, a 50 km radius between the food production site and the port was also established. The final operation is carried out by a truck and vessel combination. The summary of vessels and time associated to maintenance tasks is indicated in Table 4.

Table 4 – Summary of maintenance resources

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Time estimated</i>	<i>Vessels</i>
<i>Preventive and corrective maintenance</i>	<i>2645 h</i>	<i>CTV + ROV + AHV + TUG</i>
<i>Transport of feed and fish from/to manufacturing to site</i>	<i>22300 h</i>	<i>Truck + FSV</i>

3.4. Decommissioning and Disposal

Decommissioning and disposal are crucial aspects of LCA as they mark the EoL phase of the project and determine its management approach. The chosen strategy can significantly impact the overall environmental impact by offsetting the effects linked to earlier stages.

It was assumed that decommissioning requires almost similar operations as the installation phase. However, based on insights from previous studies, it is observed that some preceding actions might not be required. Consequently, a 15% reduction in the time needed for dismantling and removing the turbine, platform, mooring system, cage, and PV panels to shore, compared to installation, was taken into account.

Due to the high cost of implementing certain separation and recycling processes, low research and a lack of developed processes, landfills and incineration end up being the destination for some components. When not recycled, materials generally end up in landfills, contributing to the accumulation of non-biodegradable waste, compromising land use, increasing the environmental risks associated with leaching and contamination, as well as representing a loss of valuable resources. Although landfill disposal itself does not involve carbon emissions, sanitary treatment consumes resources and energy that lead to CO₂ emissions. On the other hand, residues that are normally incinerated have a much greater negative impact when analysing carbon footprint, since the process involves significant inputs and outputs, such as energy and residues.

For the baseline scenario, the disposal strategy involves directing 100% of removed materials and residues to landfill or incineration. This assumes that waste management is under the competence of the national government, with these measures being then implemented in Spain. The impact of transportation to the final disposal site is relatively minimal compared to other stages in the life cycle and is therefore not included in the analysis. The EoL considered for the baseline scenario is indicated in Table 5

Table 5 – Summary of EoL considered for the baseline scenario

Material	EoL
<i>Steel</i>	<i>Landfill</i>
<i>Nylon</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Glass fibre</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Cast iron</i>	<i>Landfill</i>
<i>Copper</i>	<i>Landfill</i>
<i>Tin</i>	<i>Landfill</i>
<i>Aluminium</i>	<i>Landfill</i>
<i>Zinc</i>	<i>Landfill</i>
<i>Polyethylene</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Glass</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Silicon</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Ethylene Vinyl Acetate</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Epoxy Resin</i>	<i>Incineration</i>

4. Baseline Impacts Result

A range of carbon factors (g CO₂ eq) [3] was applied to each unit of material or process to estimate the overall embodied carbon. As previously mentioned, the emissions attributed to the mooring system are distributed based on the proportion of masses between the wind and aquaculture systems, as this component is shared by both. The breakdown of carbon emissions per phase for each subsystem is detailed in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Carbon emissions per phase for wind and aquaculture (baseline)

The evaluation of the baseline scenario reveals that in the context of the wind energy system, manufacturing is responsible for the most significant factor at 68%, which is aligned with findings from LCA studies on wind energy. Subsequently, O&M accounts for the second-largest impact at 12%. According to [12], the impact on the O&M phase for wind energy may vary from 5% to 28%, depending on the detail of failure assessment and reliability considered. Assuming the number of elements and long distances from the supply chain, transport contributes to around 10% of the total impact. Similarly, the disposal phase also has a significant impact (10%), when it is assumed that a large proportion of the materials are destined for landfill or incineration processes. The total carbon emissions of the wind energy system correspond to 31 g CO₂ eq /kWh. Currently, the carbon emissions associated with floating offshore wind technologies are estimated to range between 11.5 to 38.1 g CO₂ eq /kwh, depending on the type of technology, site deployment, O&M strategy, and supply chain.

Comprising the aquaculture system, the total emissions correspond to 1235 g CO₂ per kg of fish produced. According to results found in the literature [17], the impact for aquaculture projects considering net cages may range approximately from 2000 to 3600 g CO₂ per kg of fish produced, varying according to species and feed approach, and system boundaries among other aspects. It is important to note that in this study the mooring system is shared with the wind energy device, which leads to a reduced potential impact on the AquaWind project.

Contrary to the results observed for the wind device, the aquaculture operations exert the most significant impact (67%). Despite efforts to minimize maintenance requirements at the aquaculture system, the main operational impact derives from regular feeding operations. With a high demand for feed, as well as structural and stability restrictions on silo capacity, frequent trips to refill the system are expected to produce a considerable impact. In addition, the transport tasks associated with moving fish for growth and post-harvest are also greatly affected by distances, contributing to overall emissions.

On the other hand, besides featuring lighter elements than the wind device, most of the aquaculture components can be manufactured at shorter distances from the Canary Islands, leading to a lower impact on manufacturing and transport to the assembly site. Related to the manufacturing phase (30%), the production of feed throughout the life of the project is the element with the most significant impact (88%).

5. Circular strategies

A circular economy seeks to enhance the efficiency of material usage, minimize resource extraction from nature, reduce waste generation, and maximize the value of products across their lifecycles. Understanding the key impacts and drivers is essential for developing effective strategies to reduce the overall carbon footprint. By identifying major and integrating circular economy principles, waste and emissions can be reduced while improving resource efficiency.

Design for circularity is a proactive design to maximise the sustainability potential of a circular economy with a balanced mix of many strategies. This may involve optimising resources, advancing recycling technologies, promoting innovative reuse practices, using new materials, and extending the life of products.

A framework has been delineated to integrate circular strategies into the design, operation and EoL approach within the AquaWind project, as illustrated in Figure 7, and will be further explored in the following sections.

Figure 7 – Framework of proposed circular strategies for AquaWind Project (adapted from [18])

5.1. Dematerialisation

Considering that choice of material has a significant impact on overall carbon emissions, the optimization in this phase is crucial to have a more environmentally friendly project.

Dematerialisation is defined as a reduction of raw materials at the production stage, of energy and material inputs at the use stage, and of waste at the disposal stage.

Although floating offshore wind turbines are experiencing rapid development, achieving economic competitiveness remains crucial to reaching market acceptability. This involves considering structural reductions in the initial design phase to optimise the overall design, while increasing economic viability and minimize environmental impact.

Given that the platform structure accounts for the highest material demand, there is a compelling opportunity for design optimization. This involves considering dynamics and structural loads to cut down material requirements. For this analysis, a deduction of 5% of platform steel is proposed to assess potential CO₂ reductions. Alternative materials have been proposed and studied for blade manufacturing, aiming to substitute traditional glass fibre and offer enhanced performance, durability, and sustainability.

Carbon fibre-reinforced polymers have gained considerable attention in the wind turbine industry. Unlike glass fibre, carbon fibre is a material with lower density, requiring fewer raw materials during production. While it presents advantages such as reduction of gearbox and structure loads and reduced transport emissions, these benefits may not fully offset the significant emissions associated with blades of this composition. Despite its lower relative mass, the environmental impacts of

manufacturing processes are higher compared to glass fibre-based components. Furthermore, the incineration of carbon fibres at the EoL stage releases a substantial amount of carbon dioxide, further escalating the environmental burdens [19]. That said, hybrid materials, consisting of approximately 85% glass fibre and 15% carbon fibre, have emerged as a potential solution. While emissions per unit mass of material are relatively similar to those of glass fibre, the hybrid approach offers the advantage of reduced blade mass. Thus, for this evaluation, hybrid material was considered.

Furthermore, within the aquaculture system, feed is the component that contributes most to the overall impact of the activity. Better feed management and reduction of losses hold potential for reducing the annual feed requirement. One proposed approach is to decrease the FCR from 2 to 1.7. Additionally, enhancing the impact of dietary supply involves considering alternative raw materials in the baseline feed. Incorporating maize gluten meal as a protein source in fish feed diminishes reliance on marine-origin resources, thereby mitigating environmental impact, as the energy required in maize gluten meal production is lower than that of fish meal. According to [17], this approach manages to maintain the nutritional needs and growth rates of the biomass. However, a more in-depth study is recommended to evaluate it from an animal welfare perspective, targeting specific fish species.

On the scope of this study, this strategy aims to lower the demand for feed, and consequently reduces fuel consumption as this approach minimises vessel operations during the refuelling phase of routine activities. Results are presented in this section for the set of proposed approaches for dematerialisation.

Figure 8 - Comparative carbon emissions for wind energy system (dematerialisation)

Figure 9 - Comparative carbon emissions for aquaculture system (dematerialisation)

Based on these assumptions, the carbon footprint reductions for wind energy and aquaculture devices are estimated at 3% and 6%, respectively. For wind energy, this translates to a total of 30g CO₂ eq/kWh, while for aquaculture, it amounts to 1156 g CO₂ eq/kg of fish produced. Slight variations may be observed across the manufacturing, transport, and disposal phases for the wind component. Conversely, significant impacts are noted during the manufacturing and operating stages of aquaculture. This is primarily due to the regular supply and transport of feed, which is highly dependent on feed conversion rate, feed system autonomy and distance from shore, despite the relatively lower demand for structure and other materials.

5.2. Recycle, Reuse and Repurpose

Implementing recycling, reuse and repurposing initiatives is the basis of circular strategies aimed at minimising the overall carbon footprint. While recycling alludes to the transformation processes of disposal residues to a useful resource, reuse implies using the material for its original or similar purpose without significant alterations. Repurposing materials involves finding new uses for items that would otherwise be discarded, thereby diverting waste from landfills.

Components made of metals generally have good recyclability potential. However, recycling wind turbine blades presents significant challenges due to their composition. Composite materials present significant complexity in the separation process, are highly energy-intensive and often degrade in value even when successfully extracted. Repurposing wind turbine blades presents an alternative strategy to recycling, aiming to find innovative uses for the blades which could involve transforming them into new

products or structures, such as architectural elements, furniture, or infrastructure components. The EoL strategy for solar panels may involve recycling the panels to recover the component materials and reusing them for the later manufacture of similar devices or other products.

Some components require chemical or mechanical separation processes to obtain the raw material before the recycling process. For this reason, it is not possible to save 100% of the carbon emissions from the raw material, as some energy is still required. Additionally, during the recycling process, some material inevitably gets lost or degraded. The assumed EoL scenarios and respective recyclability rate are indicated in Table 6.

Table 6 – Summary of circular EoL strategy (Recycle, Reuse and Repurpose)

<i>Material</i>	<i>EoL</i>	<i>Recyclability Rate</i>
<i>Steel</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>85%</i>
<i>Nylon</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>100%</i>
<i>Glass fibre + Epoxy Resin</i>	<i>Repurpose</i>	<i>100%</i>
<i>Cast iron</i>	<i>Reuse</i>	<i>100%</i>
<i>Copper</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>90%</i>
<i>Tin</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>90%</i>
<i>Aluminium</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>90%</i>
<i>Zinc</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>90%</i>
<i>Polymers</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>80%</i>
<i>Glass</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>90%</i>
<i>Silicon</i>	<i>Recycle</i>	<i>80%</i>

The comparison between the baseline and the described disposal strategy impacts are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

Figure 10 – Comparative carbon emissions for wind energy system (baseline vs. recycle, reuse and repurpose)

Figure 11 - Comparative carbon emissions for aquaculture system (baseline vs. recycle, reuse and repurpose)

By considering a more sustainable EoL strategy the carbon footprint has the potential to be reduced by 12% and 1% for wind and aquaculture devices, respectively. As the wind energy system has a greater impact related to materials, a more significant reduction was already expected. In addition, most of the material elements are made of steel, a material with great recycling potential. It's also worth mentioning that the second main contributor is the blades. In this case, a reuse strategy was chosen, which means that 100% of the impact on the materials (fibreglass and epoxy resin) can be deducted from the total amount. Following the same rationale for reusing the cast iron of the anchors, the total amount of emissions can be deducted, also contributing to further minimising the impact.

5.3. End-of-Life Extension

By maximizing the use of existing assets, the need for new construction and its associated emissions is minimized. This approach aligns with sustainability goals by conserving resources and promoting efficient use of infrastructure. However, challenges such as technological obsolescence, safety concerns, regulatory compliance, and environmental impacts must be carefully managed to ensure the long-term viability and effectiveness of extending the operational life of devices.

Due to its significant economic advantage, the continuous monitoring of structural health and the adoption of condition-based maintenance strategies for offshore devices have been demonstrated as a viable alternative to conservative design and operational approaches for extending their lifetime [20]. Structural integrity monitoring allows for the re-evaluation of offshore assets, guaranteeing an acceptable annual probability of failure to maintain performance, and potentially extending their lifespan. The current estimated operational life of offshore wind turbines is 25 years and is expected to reach 30 years within the next decade, considering technological developments allowing for more reliable designs.

This analysis took into account that the devices were designed to operate for a lifespan of 30 years without the need for additional major replacements beyond those already accounted for. Additionally, inspection and monitoring were implemented to ensure that there is no increase in the failure rate typically observed in trends indicated by the bathtub curve, which relates to the ageing and deterioration of components. The comparative results are indicated in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

Figure 12 - Comparative carbon emissions for wind energy system (baseline vs. lifetime extension)

Figure 13 - Comparative carbon emissions for aquaculture system (baseline vs. lifetime extension)

This framework outlines a potential reduction of 11% and 1% for wind and aquaculture, respectively. This reduction is primarily driven by the offsetting impacts resulting from increased energy and fish production within the initial system. Despite the increase in biomass production towards the end of its lifespan, operational and maintenance (O&M) activities remain the predominant factor influencing impacts, particularly due to the need for periodic refuelling trips for feed over time. This dynamic sustains consistent demand over an additional 5-year period, implying that the reduction in impact is more closely linked to the integration of other phases into the final biomass increase. The final carbon footprint observed under the lifetime extension approach is 28 g eq CO₂/kWh for wind and 1220 g eq CO₂/kg fish and aquaculture systems.

5.4. Combination of several strategies

The previously proposed strategies encompass key aspects for improved resource management, potentially yielding greater value from them. These strategies were individually analysed with a focus on reducing, recycling, reusing, repurposing, and extending the lifetime of resources. This section aims to evaluate the coexistence of all proposed approaches to enhance the benefits brought by the implementation of circular strategies. The outcomes from combined approaches are shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15.

Figure 14 - Comparative carbon emissions for wind energy system (combination of circular strategies)

Figure 15 - Comparative carbon emissions for aquaculture system (combination of circular strategies)

The total carbon emissions from the implementation of these principles indicate 24 g CO₂ eq/kWh for wind components and 1138 g CO₂ eq/kg fish for aquaculture, with an overall reduction of 24% and 8%, respectively.

As expected, the most significant impacts occur during the manufacturing and disposal phases, both for wind and aquaculture. This underscores the importance of better resource management.

Considering reducing material demand not only leads to decreased fuel consumption for transportation but also contributes to waste reduction. Furthermore, selecting best practices for the EoL of elements is crucial for achieving a more eco-friendly system and aligning with the sustainable objectives of the project.

It is important to highlight that these suggestions are limited to an analysis of CO₂ emissions and should be examined from a broader perspective, considering technological, economic, and regulatory contexts. A holistic approach is essential to fully understand the implications and optimize the proposed strategies, ensuring comprehensive sustainability considerations beyond carbon emissions.

Conclusions

Within the scope of the AquaWind project, a model involving a high-level LCA was developed to estimate the carbon footprint of a full-scale MUP consisting of a wind turbine and a coupled aquaculture cage. This assessment aimed to estimate the carbon footprint and identify the main contributors for such emissions and propose circular strategies to minimize impacts. Data collection was conducted based on information shared by project partners for a 1:6 prototype, complemented by sources from literature, industry, and internal expertise.

The outcomes demonstrate relative alignment with results found in the literature, validating the proposed model. Material requirements and end-of-life approaches emerge as the most critical aspects influencing carbon emissions. Particularly for the aquaculture component, ensuring robust biomass growth for commercial market size requires impactful regular operation for feed supply, heavily influenced by the distance from shore. On the other hand, the benefits of MUP are highlighted by the notable decrease in impact attributed to the shared mooring system and minimisation of materials, in comparison to exclusive projects. Furthermore, exploring synergies within maintenance resources is promising for further diminishing the overall environmental footprint.

By introducing circular principles into the AquaWind project, the strategies proposed are founded on three main pillars of design for circularity:

- Dematerialisation: focusing on reducing material usage and minimising waste.
- Cyclical use of resources: implementing best practices for recycling, reusing, and repurposing resources to add value to materials and reduce waste.
- Lifetime extension: prolonging the device's operational lifespan to extract its maximum value, thereby reducing the need for new components and materials, and minimizing residues.

Focusing on circular design at an early stage is the most immediate strategy for minimising the extraction of raw materials and end-of-life waste. By focusing on optimising structures and components and diversifying into less carbon-intensive and lighter alternative materials, such as hybrid fibreglass-carbon composites, it is possible to significantly reduce carbon emissions. Reconsidering the management of fish feed to reduce FCR and substituting meals with a lower embodied carbon footprint, while ensuring nutritional and welfare standards, appears to be a viable approach to reducing carbon emissions associated with aquaculture production. Reducing distances between manufacturing and operation, also seems to be a key aspect to be considered.

Furthermore, a key aspect of fundamental design principles involves considering materials that have the potential to be reintroduced to the flow by being recycled, reused, or repurposed. These are crucial considerations not only for emissions impacts reduction, but also given the ongoing competition for scarce resources and the need to lessen the dependence on virgin materials.

The development of more reliable components that increase durability and repairability, coupled with improved preventive maintenance, also enables the prolongation of project lifetimes, contributing to a more sustainable and efficient use of resources.

The findings indicate that the synergy between several circularity principles can boost the impact minimisation. Combining the three proposed strategies, a potential for reductions of 24% and 8% were identified for wind and aquaculture systems, respectively. However, this study limited its analysis to the embodied carbon footprint of the project, suggesting a need to broaden the analysis scope to include additional environmental burdens, as well as technological, economic, and regulatory aspects.

The potential benefits of incorporating a set of circular design principles are evident and must be pursued. However, the approach must be adapted to the specific context of the project and requires a holistic view that considers the complexities and unique challenges of each application.

It is essential to recognise that implementing such strategies comes with significant challenges. It is important to implement standards for waste treatment to ensuring that recycled materials meet consistent and high-quality standards, supporting the broader goals of circular economy. Additionally, technological developments are still ongoing aiming to improve performance, reduce environmental burdens and achieve economic feasibility, both for recycling processes and for component durability and reliability improvements. Similarly, the market chain must be unlocked and stimulated to accommodate secondary materials.

The results of this report attempt to be as accurate as possible based on the inputs available at the time of study completion. However, limitations regarding information on certain design specifications, materials and manufacturing processes have led to some assumptions to facilitate the study, which consequently aggregates a certain level of uncertainty. Although the results may not precisely reflect a real final implementation scenario for a commercial project, this model has proved its value by offering useful insights into the implementation of the circular economy principles into the AquaWind project. Further refinement of the results can be carried out as the project progresses and can be evaluated in the forecasted deliverable D4.4.

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